

THE EFFECT OF SELF-ASSESSMENT ON STUDENT ENGAGEMENT IN MATHEMATICS: ANALYZING CHANGES IN ENGAGEMENT LEVELS

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Abstract

Assessment, including self-assessment, provides a rich scaffolding for the growth and improvement of students. The study evaluated whether there is evidence of development in the three dimensions of student engagement as influenced by self-assessment. Forty-eight students of a private university in the Philippines who were enrolled in a general mathematics course were the participants of the study. The participants underwent a self-assessment scheme by including weekly narrative self-assessment journals, assessment checklists, and student portfolios in the instruction. Levels of student engagement were gauged using a student engagement scale in a pre-test and post-test design. The comparison outcomes showed varying levels of engagement in the affective, cognitive, and behavioral dimensions. Also, the results suggest evidence of the effectiveness of self-assessment in improving student engagement on the three dimensions of engagement. Contents of the student reflections in the study have further proven the usefulness of self-assessment activities in the mathematics learning experience.

Keywords: Student Engagement, Self-Assessment, Formative Assessment, Mathematics Learning, Mathematics Education.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the central problems in the mathematics classroom is students' lack of motivation and disengagement with mathematics. Student engagement plays a vital role in the academic environment since it is a major predictor of students' learning, grades, achievement test scores, mathematical confidence, retention, and graduation (Carini et al., 2006; Everingham et al., 2017; Fredricks et al., 2004; Konold et al., 2018; Skilling et al., 2020). However, more and more students feel worried, apprehensive, anxious and apathetic about learning because they find themselves in learning situations where the subject is too challenging, confusing, daunting, or pointless which leads to students being labeled as 'slow learner', 'disadvantaged', 'weak', etc. (Bishop & Kalogeropoulos, 2015; Skilling et al., 2020).

Studies have revealed the compensatory effect of engagement in which students who are least prepared academically benefit more from engagement than those who are most prepared, in relation to effects on grades and persistence (Carini et al., 2006). An in-the-moment engagement, although a dynamically evolving construct, is highly malleable as it intently involves individuals' experienced needs, goals, desires, and meaningful purposes (Goldin, 2017). Students who value learning engagement will likely develop habits of mind that enhance continuous learning and personal development that they carry even after college. When students are required to take responsibility for activities that require daily decisions and tasks, they are invested in the activity and become more committed to their studies (Kuh et al., 2008). Engagement paired with motivation marks

the first stages of learning (Shulman, 2002). Teacher-student interaction plays an important role in influencing student engagement and motivation (Durksen et al., 2017). In this direction, defining engagement constructs identifies the teaching and learning conditions that are effective for helping increasingly diverse students to acquire the knowledge, dispositions, skills, and competencies demanded by future circumstances. In exploring the relationships of student engagement and learning outcomes, Kong, Wong and Lam (Kong et al., 2003) identified and instrumentalized engagement constructs: behavioral, cognitive, and affective. In this platform, student engagement is truly a complex multi-dimensional learning factor. This study used self-assessment in a classroom practice as a response to one of the central problems in the teaching of mathematics which is on the academic disengagement of learners. Knowing that academic disengagement is malleable (Durksen et al., 2017; Goldin, 2017; Mulqueeny et al., 2015), it can be reshaped through classroom practices.

Classroom assessment of mathematical competency is more focused on summative gains. Research show that the use of formative authentic assessment tools valuably enhances student learning and performance in mathematics. Among the array of authentic assessment tools, self-assessment is increasingly utilized in the learning process. Self-assessment as a formative assessment, consists of a set of classroom procedures where teachers, students or their peers become aware of personal progress in their skills, processes, or attitudes, and in identifying strengths and weaknesses in students' work for an appropriate revision (Black & William, 2009). It may be unpredicted that students are more aware of their cognitive and affective features compared to their teachers and they are also aware that the teaching strategy is not fit for them thus causing a feeling of exclusion and further disengagement (Bishop & Kalogeropoulos, 2015). Addressing such issue need strategies where students are encouraged to discuss their individual thoughts, opinions, ideas, and approaches in learning mathematics which help make students' values more apparent and thus help in an active engagement with mathematics (Andrade & du, 2007; Bishop & Kalogeropoulos, 2015; Clarkson et al., 2019).

A self-assessment program which comprised of analysis and reflection of the incorrect points on the solution and where feedback on such reflection was given had effectively improved students' performance in the final exam (Cabedo & Maset-Llaudes, 2019). Apart from improving student performance, self-assessment, as a formative assessment, leads to positive changes in the learner's behaviour through self-awareness and developing the understanding of the learner's own learning. A summary of these benefits include students' awareness of ability upon checking-out their own learning, goal-oriented motivation where students can identify their own learning progress, promotion of learning after the recognition of what needs to be learned, sharing of the assessment role shifting from something imposed to a potential partnership, promotion of critical thinking and meta-cognitive behaviour, increased responsibility for own learning, and confidence in doing mathematics (Beumann & Wegner, 2018). Improvement in learning is also reported in the use of self-assessment in an online course and the use of learning apps on

smartphones (Barzel et al., 2019; Hwang et al., 2015). The gains of using self-assessment applies in different learning platforms.

Since most of the studies focused on the effect of self-assessment on student achievement gains, this study contributes to the literature on self-assessment and student engagement by focusing on the influence of the self-assessment intervention in mathematics learning to the affective/emotional, behavioral, and cognitive dimensions of student engagement. This study departs from the socio-cultural theoretical perspective in mathematics learning. Student engagement is regarded as a multi-dimensional construct tapping on different facets of learning. On this account, this study adapted a student engagement framework (Kong et al., 2003) for conceptualizing and measuring engagement, categorizing student engagement into three main dimensions: affective/emotional, behavioral, and cognitive.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research Design

The focus of the study is on the effect of self-assessment in student engagement in mathematics learning. Self-assessment and student engagement are both qualitative in nature; however, the measure of student engagement can be done in quantitative ways, through the use of an engagement scale designed for the mathematics classroom. The general system for data gathering adapted the pre-test post-test without control group design.

2.2. Sample

The study was conducted in one private university in the Philippines. The duration of the intervention was eight (8) weeks, covering two terms of the semester, the midterm and the final term. This allowed for a completion of four Algebra topics. The 8 weeks covered a total of 21 days excluding suspension of classes due to national holidays and typhoons.

Participants of the study were students enrolled in one general mathematics course for one semester. Initially, 51 students participated in the study; however, only 48 students completed the entire process. The group consisted of students majoring in Hospitality and Tourism Management; Hotel, Resort and Restaurant Management; and Entrepreneurship. Participants were in their first year of study with the exception of two who were in their third year.

2.3. Research Instrument

In measuring student engagement, the study adopted the Student Engagement in a Mathematics Classroom Scale (Kong et al., 2003). The instrument has been validated, and though proven reliable using Cronbach's Alpha, it has been tested again for reliability since it was used in a culturally different group of students, and instead of having it in a 5-point Likert scale as in the original questionnaire, the study adapted a 6-point Likert scale for a higher degree of discrimination between levels. All the items were put to a 6-point Likert scale except for items on *time-spent on task*. The reliability testing made use

of Cronbach's Alpha and yielded an index of 0.81 which is within the accepted level of reliability.

2.4. Data Collection Procedure

To minimize the disruption of the academic process, the self-assessment was given to the students as a part of an out-of-the-classroom activity. As part of the university's standard procedure for research, the self-assessment activity was given on a voluntary basis. It was also explained to the respondents that their self-assessment outputs will be used for research, hence informed consent was obtained from the respondents, highlighting that their responses will be used anonymously in the data analysis. Although it was in a voluntary basis, all students opted to participate, however, only 48 out of the 51 students finished the entire 8-week self-assessment intervention.

The self-assessment tasks included assessment rubrics, self-assessment checklists, weekly narrative self-assessment reports and end-term portfolio. These along with their accomplished class activities such as quizzes, homework, seatwork and exams, were the basis for the feedback. Self-assessment activities also aided in the further analysis of the different constructs under the dimensions of student engagement. These data gathering tools are considered valid and reliable if they complied with the following: the information requested is known to the respondents; the questions are phrased clearly and unambiguously; the questions refer to recent activities; the respondents think the questions merit a thoughtful response; the information requested is potentially verifiable; and the question asks for information that is known to those answering the questions and does not threaten, embarrass, or violate their privacy or encourage the respondent to respond in socially desirable ways (Carini et al., 2006). The journal prompts used in the journal writing process complied with the three aspects of learning mathematics (Urquhart, 2009) namely: content, process, and affective. The journal writing scheme closely followed the metric system strategy, which included set of questions to be reflected upon.

The self-assessment procedure adapted Four-Stage Model for Self-Assessment (Rolheiser & Ross, 2001). The first stage was concerned about involving students in defining the criteria that were used to judge their performance. Performance pertained to all the activities involved in the instruction. The criteria also described the levels of proficiency. Hence, before any activity the assessment rubric was given and explained to the students. The rubric included the specific criteria of evaluation and the descriptive levels of proficiency. This gave the students a clear view of what was expected of them, so they would put appropriate action to each activity.

The second stage involved applying the criteria to their work. The rubric served as a guide for each activity. Upon the submission of an activity, the student accomplished a self-assessment checklist which included how the students prepared for the activity, as well as their accomplishment for each activity. It was also in this stage where students drafted a student report detailing their appraisal of their performance in a week. This served as an avenue for them to reflect on their performance and understanding of the lessons in

class, as well as the time devoted for an out-of-class enrichment activity. Guide questions were used to direct students in writing their journal. The items included in the checklist as well as the guide questions closely mirror the engagement constructs used in the student engagement scale. These helped the students set their goal for the next discussion and activities in class allowing them to determine the amount of effort necessary for the action plan.

The third stage involved giving students feedback on their self-evaluations. Feedback was given in association to the analysis on the weekly student narrative self-assessment report and class performance. It is most important to give objective, appropriate and on-time feedback to preserve the authenticity of the tool. The feedback for the quizzes and homework were given on the class meeting after it was submitted along with the rated activity. Since reading the narrative report took longer time, the feedback on their journal was given a week after it was submitted, before they submit the next journal.

The last stage was to allow students to develop productive goals and action plans which were reflected on every journal that was submitted. Items on the weekly journal included questions like *What are your goals for the following week?* and *What would you do differently next time*, which helped students to detail what they plan to do for the following week, addressing their weaknesses and insufficiencies. Every activity including the reflections was compiled in a portfolio. The Retell-Relate-Reflect model for the portfolio and the rubric for scoring were adopted from a portfolio framework (Rolheiser & Schwartz, 2001). In the portfolio, students provided a reflection on their selected activities guided with the prompts found in the rubric.

2.5. Data Analysis

After eight weeks of doing the self-assessment procedure, the students used the student engagement scale as a post-test. Their responses on the pre-test and post-test were interpreted for the median level of engagement using six (6) categories: highly engaged, engaged, moderately engaged, moderately disengaged, disengaged, and highly disengaged. The set of categories on the degrees of agreement used on the engagement scale was matched with an appropriate set of categories on the level of engagement. The matched levels were strongly agree=highly engaged, agree=engaged, somewhat agree=moderately engaged, somewhat disagree=moderately disengaged, disagree=disengaged and strongly disagree=highly disengaged. Responses from the pre-test and post-test were also statistically analyzed for significant differences using Wilcoxon Signed-rank Test.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Data collected from students' responses on the student engagement scale revealed their median level of engagement before and after the intervention, as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Level of engagement before and after the self-assessment practice

Engagement Dimensions	Level of Engagement	
	Pre-intervention	Post-intervention
<i>Affective</i>		
Interest	Moderately Engaged	Engaged
Achievement Orientation	Highly Engaged	Highly Engaged
Anxiety	Disengaged	Disengaged
Frustration	Engaged	Engaged
<i>Cognitive</i>		
Surface Strategy	Moderately Disengaged	Moderately Disengaged
Deeper Strategies	Moderately Engaged	Engaged
Reliance	Engaged	Engaged
<i>Behavioral</i>		
Attentiveness	Engaged	Engaged
Diligence/ Persistence	Engaged	Engaged

Generally, the results show that there was a recorded increase in the level of engagement on the dimensions after the self-assessment procedure, although not every increase is significant.

In an 8-week period of being through the self-assessment practice, analysis of students' pre-test and post-test on the student engagement scale revealed significant differences on some areas of engagement. Wilcoxon signed-rank test at 0.05 level of significance showed a statistically significant change for interest ($Z=-4.439$, $p= 0.000$) and frustration ($Z=-2.420$, $p= 0.016$) constructs of the affective dimension of engagement. Also, there was a statistically significant change for the cognitive constructs, surface strategies ($Z=-2.119$, $p=0.034$) and deep strategies ($Z=-2.870$, $p=0.004$). For the behavioral dimension, there was a significant change in the attentiveness ($Z=-2.459$, $p=0.14$) and time spent of task ($Z=-2.394$, $p=0.17$).

Students' written responses from the self-assessment activities validate the above statistical result. The students highlighted the relevance of the self-assessment activities on their improvement in class. Most of their responses included reflections on their strengths, weaknesses and shortcomings in some areas of mathematics learning.

3.1. Affective/Emotional Engagement

On the affective dimension of student engagement, the results show that students have increased levels of affective engagement in mathematics learning and this increase is significant in the interest and frustration constructs. This is supported by their responses in the weekly journals and reflections included in the portfolio such as,

“What was significantly meaningful was being able to prove to myself that even [if] I hated Math before, I can still learn how to love this subject now.”

Some students also generalized their preference for some topics on the course and recognize the value of mathematics in their lives.

“The part [of journal writing] that I like the most is the part that we are given the chance to write the problems that we are encountering. It really helped us a lot. Now I understand that journal writing is for our own good.”

The students realized the value of the self-assessment tools which persuaded them to give importance to their learning and to the self-assessment activities. Also, the feedback portion of the self-assessment process motivated a student to seek improvement in learning. One student wrote,

“I can see my teacher’s feedback [on] my positive outlooks and [it] motivates me in correcting my mistakes.”

For students, feedback is beneficial for understanding and gaining from the assessment process and improving their work (Greene et al., 2018; Wanner & Palmer, 2018). Also, feedback is beneficial when teachers help set students’ expectations for success but has negative effects when teachers sets low expectations (Fyfe & Brown, 2020).

One of the top goals of students in learning mathematics is having high scores. They often feel satisfied if they get high scores on summative tests given in class. One factor that drives students to achieve in their academic endeavours and avoid failure is social expectations, particularly from their parents (Kong et al., 2003). In fact, one of the students wrote,

“My goals for the following week are to get high scores in our quiz and assignment...”

“...I should have a better score in the quizzes, activities and requirements.”

Some students had different views on achievement. One student explained,

“I realize now that good work is not about having a high score but it’s about being able to understand what your instructor taught you.”

“When I wrote my journal, I was not thinking about a high score, but I want to share my experiences and tell what I really feel.”

Despite knowing that the self-assessment activities were not being scored. These perspectives imply that the participants’ view of achievement does not only mean getting high scores or high grades, but on a deeper sense, it is being able to gain a sound understanding of the topics and understanding the purposes of the self-assessment activities. From this awareness, participants were also able to plan their future actions based on a success or a failure that they gained in an activity. Their reflections also highlighted one of the benefits of writing journals, that is, helping them identify their areas of strengths and weaknesses, as supported by statements like:

“...I can reflect on my weaknesses and strengths and it [journal writing] helps me improve for the next weeks.”

An engagement construct that was not significantly affected by the self-assessment activities is anxiety. It is a subject which does not often appear on the reflections written

by students in their journals and portfolio. The fear of failure or having low scores and lack of confidence contributed to the heightened anxiety of the students. Some students disliked lengthy solutions to problems because they got often confused. Not being able to fully understand the lesson and getting confused along the process were common weaknesses for most of the participants. Some students got even more frustrated because they extended their learning through watching tutorials on the web and practicing on problems outside the class hour, but still, they got confused. However, some were able to take these difficulties to their advantage, as some have written,

“Even though I got low results, I was still on track and did not lose hope, but rather it motivated me more to recover. I realized now not to take things for granted.”

Dissatisfaction and frustration are common problems with learners struggling with mathematics. However, the journal writing experience provided a narrative on the participant’s mathematics confidence. In the case of the participants, self-assessment activities were able to bring about a decrease in their emotional problems through self-reflections and awareness of their insufficiencies. This development is shown in one of the reflections:

“The worst part of writing the journal was when I did not understand the lesson and I wrote it all down, but the advantage of it is my teacher gave a feedback that motivated me to improve myself and to have an extra effort to understand the lesson.”

Students who critically review their work and set goals for improvement develop competence, exhibit positive mathematics concept, and become more committed to their studies (Andrade & du, 2007; Carini et al., 2006; Kuh, 2009; Kuh et al., 2008; Sagayadevan & Jeyaraj, 2012).

3.2. Cognitive Engagement

On the cognitive dimension of engagement, the study showed a significant difference on the surface strategies, deeper strategies, and reliance. Through self-assessment, the students became aware of their study habits and were able to identify the strategies that worked best for them as well as their preferences in learning math. The participants preferred to learn math the way it was presented in class. They patterned the solution of problems with the ones solved in class, and they insisted on memorizing the patterns of solutions. Students reported reliance on what the teacher gives. One student stated,

“I prefer to learn math by practicing the examples that the instructor is giving.”

The participants also reported seeking help from their peers on some topics that they find difficult as a strategy to understand their lessons. Peer tutoring is seen to improve mathematics achievement, mathematical fluency, and computation (Alegre et al., 2020; Greene et al., 2018).

As they got comfortable with the self-assessment process, they were able to reflect deeper on their learning strategies. They were able to prove developments in their learning strategies, as one student explained that,

“Now we understand that this subject requires patience, analysis and deep understanding. Patience because some problems have long processes, analysis because it is not about memorizing the steps, it is about logically applying the processes to the problems, deep understanding because some steps are crucial.”

Most of the students preferred to learn math by practicing on problems given in class, on some examples found in books, and even on problems found in math tutorial websites. Using the web as a learning resource can significantly increase math knowledge (Kay & Kletskin, 2012). This initial step to improve their skills has developed into being able to analyze the procedure necessary to solve a problem. This was one of the common goals appearing in the weekly journal writing. Students wanted understanding of every topic in class.

Being able to reflect over the week's lessons also improved their awareness of the skills that they are deficient in. One student wrote,

“I get to apply the new lessons and the strategies that I discovered during my homework and the skills that I improved in a week”.

Also, being able to reflect over their performance in class, some students were able to develop a sound study habit. This shift is particularly beneficial in improving mathematics achievement where memorization strategies were negatively associated with mathematics achievement, while control strategies, which include self-reflective activities, were positively associated with mathematics achievement (Areepattamannil & Caleon, 2013). Through the reflection on their performances over a week, the students were able to identify the strategies that worked best for them and reflected upon their preferences in learning math. Learning can be improved when students can identify their own learning progress, recognize what needs to be learned, and increase their responsibility for their own learning (Wanner & Palmer, 2018).

3.3. Behavioral Engagement

Behavioral changes resulting from self-assessment activities may prove to be effective in enhancing student engagement. The attentiveness of the students in class and persistence in learning math have improved. Most of the students agreed that listening attentively helped in understanding the discussions. One student wrote,

“I listened to the instructor and I carefully followed her instructions.”

Students who take their weekly goals seriously realized the need to exert more effort to achieve their goals. Students exposed to goal-setting perform significantly better than those who do not consistently do goal setting (van Lent & Souverijn, 2020). They were able to accomplish their goals using several strategies. Among these strategies were taking notes during the lecture, practicing over the problems in the discussion, diligently

reviewing their notes, and looking for other review resources. Motivated to improve their performance in class, some students took the extra effort of looking for more examples to practice on in some reference books. Some also viewed instructional videos from the web, as one of the students reported,

“...I have searched and watched a tutorial on YouTube...”

Students realized that journal writing, as a self-assessment tool, proved to be advantageous in creating a healthy study strategy, as can be reflected in one student's sharing,

“Journals helped me to study well and review everything in Math every night. For me math is a very difficult subject but with the help of the journals, I always review to recall the past lectures and learn from those.”

Not only in journal writing but even the given homework with self-assessment checklist also manifested its gains, positively compelling students to devote more time and persist to fully understand the lessons taught. As a student expressed,

“This first assignment is particularly meaningful because I worked hard for it. I spent a lot of time just to solve it correctly... Home works provide me the opportunity to assess my own understanding of that lesson.”

From the student reports, self-assessment activities proved to be helpful in improving students' behavior towards learning math. This conforms with a study that self-assessment tools are effective in improving self-reflection and eventually in improving learning among students (Lew & Schmidt, 2011).

4. CONCLUSION

The study investigated the potential of self-assessment activities in improving student engagement in mathematics learning. In this study, it is found that students have varying levels of student engagement on the affective/emotional, behavioral, and cognitive dimensions. Nonetheless, after the self-assessment intervention there was a gradual increase in student engagement. Also, it was found out that there is a significant improvement on student engagement on the levels of affective/emotional, cognitive, and behavioral dimensions upon completing the self-assessment process. As students engaged in the self-assessment procedure, they became aware of their preferences in learning, strengths and weaknesses then eventually, they learn to develop a plan for improvement. The impact of including self-assessment as an integral part of the instruction resulted in an engaged attitude towards learning mathematics, thus improving students' mathematics performance.

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